

Multi-Purpose Apps and the Social Media: What's in it for the Sustainable Development Goals and Commerce to a Social Enterprise?

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ABSTRACT

The growth rate of Social Enterprises (SE) in Malaysia marks a significant change in the development of young enterprising leaders and in their innovation to salvage for the needy towards a sharing economic model for the well-being of the underprivileged society. This paper explores the support of Social Media (SM) and other web applications used by a social enterprise in Kuala Lumpur Malaysia using a case study approach that looks into (1) the influences of SM and web apps in current business ways of work (2) readiness of the SE staff and beneficiaries to adapt and use these technologies (3) approaches to sustain business production through the digital means which are investigated based on preliminary data gathered from semi-structured interview and an online survey using the social media platform following a qualitative research framework. Findings from the study found high staff readiness to adapt and adopt these web-based apps however, these productivity tools were found to be functionally single purposed to the needs of a work process when compared to the choices of software variability and its' low-cost impact. A positive correlation is noticeable with small orders in production and delivery handling on a variety of these web and mobile platforms to the worker productivity. Additionally, social media tools consider the development of digital communities for its beneficiaries, keeping informed of the SE social impact values and the 'Sustainable Development Goals'(SDGs) and as their means to seek work opportunities. A web portal to streamline the SE activities is proposed to facilitate order placement, processing, and delivery. Further the web system is expected to offer personalized customer experience through order customization, and for improvement feedback that goes in line with the causes for the SDGs in consideration of sustainably sourced and made products ie. pre-loved items.

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KEYWORDS: sustainable development goals, social enterprise, case study, social media, web portal

INTRODUCTION

Social Media (SM) sites like Instagram and Facebook predominantly are notable personal touchpoints in engaging with customers, and a platform to operate business thus making online buying, selling activities presented in the friendly, and sociable way. For a Social Enterprise (SE), the impact to create web connections and awareness imply the importance that SM sites could bring while remaining conscientious to its social values in the decisions for resources ie. sustainably sourced and managed materials in production operations for the business bottom line. This paper objectifies the presence of SM to a SE within the variability of market ready mobile based web applications discussed upon its influences in the working ways by a SE. The paper aims to (1) identify the types of SM sites web application used by the SE in consideration of its variability and needs (2) assess the readiness of a Small and Medium SE to engage and

adapt collaborative apps in business activities along a value chain process flow juxtaposed economic value and job opportunities for the beneficiaries (3) propose a web portal in improving the many apps approach as a strategy to scale up business within sustainable production means and resources. Waste negatively impacts behaviour of the reasonable consumer, according to Huang et al. (2022) invoking responsible consumerism involves many stakeholders and one that particularly outlines the business model of a SE. The emphasis of SDGs is told in the benefit for the underprivileged and should be explored through purposeful ways. While lacking in perception is the action and people roles for the SDGs, digital tools are found to help improve the visibility of SDGs along with leadership direction, employee commitment, empowered control in decisions and performance for the business goals (Smith et al., 2022) in the social impact and value creation. Observing from needs of

“Multi-Purpose Apps and the Social Media: What’s in it for the Sustainable Development Goals and Commerce to a Social Enterprise?”

business operations in the activities, interview data and a survey was conducted with 30 respondents to gauge the perception of sustainable consumerism in the concept of pre-loved items and the SDGs. In the elements, the SDGs can be practiced in the craft, and people willingness to buy used items. In an example, the SE was able to complete a small, targeted user upcycling project within a shorter time span as these orders were not catered for a large consumer base.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Digital End-User Engagement

Apart from digitalisation, information technologies that encompasses of computing elements for the people has challenged the conventional norms of work practices as small enterprises turn to mainstream media as an attempt to embrace the digital bandwagon label in the pursuits of end-user engagement to remain competitive due to the lack in experience outcomes particularly for the young business (Abdul Kadir & Sarif, 2014; Adhiatma et al., 2022). With web development and the internet medium serving as the backbone infrastructure and platform for the products and services delivery (Satar et al., 2024; Shahid et al., 2023), communicating sustainability using digitally enhanced work activities has improved business visibility and mobility over an end-to-end supply chain to allow businesses to tap into new markets for customer and talent development in return of stakeholder benefits. However, the adverse impact from the recent pandemic situation created uncertainties to all business types including Social Enterprises (SEs) (Kamaludin et al., 2021), ‘goto’ digital media and collaborative apps lends as shortcuts to access and implement a type of cloud service that could bear between zero or little operating cost when planned according to a simpler operating model, bearing importance for its social value proposition (Chauhan et al., 2022).

“We knew about all these shortcuts of ways to reach out, to get things done using systems, free team apps, like team working apps like Trello, like Air Table, like Canva. I think all those things was only known when we pushed ourselves beyond the comfort zone where we had to work together but somehow apart.”, CEO of SE X.

Being a vertically challenged organization, the SEs have limiting resources to spare and under these circumstances perform multifaceted tasks while acquiring and developing skillsets over a digital learning curve. Similarly, the multi-purpose apps present a variety of functionalities for the end-user experience but are mostly found underutilized to process custom-specific tasks seamlessly than anticipated (Elsantil, 2020). Although these cloud conduit public domain and multi-functional web-apps offer a unified platform for the mass user, work routines are still found silo operational for the goals, user-experience, and performance of the business operating model (Mink, 2023). In contrast to single tasking apps, the versatility of multi-purpose apps supports an agile,

and responsive product design process, as it improves stakeholder engagement, from ideation to the deployment of a minimum viable product while facilitating communication in commerce and United Nation’s Sustainability Development Goals (SDGs) (Smith et al., 2022). Furthermore, the integration of multi-purpose apps with social media platforms contribute to the development of responsible consumerism and commerce to advance the SE commitment and causes for a sustainably developed business.

Social Enterprise Call for Action in Alignment with the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) – The Digital Alternative

Cavalcanti (2020) regards the occupation of a social entrepreneur in pursuant of a social mission who plays an essential role to advocate the causes of both business and societal values through encouraged collaboration and interactive communication (Sebhatu & Enquist, 2022) in the context of smaller work settings. However, the reality often blurs when business survival needs ie. resources and capital (Smith et al., 2022) conditions the growth trajectory of the SE solely for their social causes. Ideally, a social enterprise operates with a triple-bottom-line approach, considering social, environmental, and the economic impact simultaneously. While the SE social impact can be measured in both the positive influences that considers choices like empowering the underserved society and taking action to safeguard the planet, it is also said that alternatively within the context of commerce platforms, these SDG elements can be infused in design and deployed as a framework to guide an organization’s commitment to sustainability and social responsibility (Friedrich, 2019). In retrospect, it takes a team to pulls off an extraordinary task into action for their beneficiaries in reducing inequalities when the situation warrants it. Coincidentally, having the representation of a SE to advocate ethical consumerism that improves with the availability of free cloud-serviced digital platforms to choose from in consideration of SDG 12 Sustainable Consumption and Production (*‘THE 17 GOALS’*, n.d.).

“It’s not something that we normally do. It’s just that when we see dim fit, because when our tailor akka is super, super committed, we want to empower her in a certain way. She knows that she can earn an income if she has a better machine and that’s what the team comes together to do. And then we decide you know what, let’s do it, let’s squeeze the little bit of our cash flow and get her sewing machine” , CEO of SE X.

Rashid et al. (2019) suggests conscious consumerism is influenced by the presence and extensive social media reach when in use as a cost-effective marketing strategy (Pakura & Rudeloff, 2020) able improved customer interaction and brand experience. In fact, leveraging on popular social media as a commerce platform improves direct sales besides offering micro-entrepreneurship opportunities to the

“Multi-Purpose Apps and the Social Media: What’s in it for the Sustainable Development Goals and Commerce to a Social Enterprise?”

marginalized communities in the access of untapped and competitive markets (Wang & Xie ,2020). Inadvertently, social commerce creates a conducive space for consumer engagement and dialogue among peers in the support of digital communities and call for action by the SE’s shared objectives in alignment with the SDGs like Goal 8 Decent Work and Economic Growth (*‘THE 17 GOALS’*,n.d.). Additionally, value creation can be enhanced when the SDGs are used as a framework to guide the implementation of work practices that encourages a learning culture following a priority order of action and impact measured in the efforts to communicate sustainability commitment to the stakeholders (Climent and Haftor, 2021) while addressing environmental and societal challenges (Gigauri & Damenia, 2021).

“She will share me videos of the Akka sewing and they themselves when they meet up to the at the Community Center to discuss how to do a certain product, they are laughing, they are enjoying their time, they gossip, they have girls, women’s

time not just as colleagues, they talk about family, they talk about hardship”, CEO of SE X.

METHOD

Research Design

A mixed method design approach was implemented in the study using an online survey as primary data source based on a Likert scale (1-Strong Disagree 2-Disagree 3-Neutral 4-Agree 5-Strongly Agree) that was developed with 5 close-ended questions on the awareness of the SDGs, perceived quality of second-hand purchases like pre-loved items and the buyer motivation. Additionally, a semi-structured interview with the SE was carried out to further understand the implications of SM, in sales and marketing and operations management using current web app tools. The questions delved on the types of web tools used to engage with clients and staff, tools for work collaboration, production operations and delivery. Table 1 lists some of the web app tools identified and their specific functions in addition to SM customer engagement web systems.

Table 1: Collaborative apps used by Social Enterprise X

App Name	Purpose
Trello	Organize projects, and task built in list prioritized to handle work completion and deadlines used collaboratively by three members of the SE. Links with Teams, Google Drive, and other applications.
Canva	Platform used in integration with AirTable for projects and product orders apart from events planning using SM platforms that embed visualization and design clarity, quick and effortlessly. Links with pre-recorded audio, video, with attractive designs.
AirTable	App that manages customer orders, with a feature to track orders, over premade CRM template finishing sales to delivery workspace and performance records start to finish.
Easy Parcel with Lalamove	App that offers a scheduled last-mile delivery of orders with real-time tracking, as flexible and cost-efficient solution

Using a thematic analysis, interview data gathered are interpreted for ideas to derive suggestive themes by creating a relationship of concepts that runs in an overview of steps

such as code work, generating and naming themes for the reporting of data investigated (Ho, et al., 2023). Table 2 and 3 each presents the recorded data.

Table 2: Online Survey Responses

Factors	(N=30)					%				
Awareness of SDGs	1	2	3	4	5					
1. Recognise SDGs from targets	6	6	2	11	5	20	20	6.7	36.7	16.7
2. SDG influences shopping online and choices.	12	10	2	4	2	40	33.3	6.7	13.3	6.7
Perceived Online Product Quality										

“Multi-Purpose Apps and the Social Media: What’s in it for the Sustainable Development Goals and Commerce to a Social Enterprise?”

3. Expectations in the quality of online purchases.											
- Durable and long lasting											
- Meets and exceeds expectations.	5	1	2	14	8	16.7	3.3	6.7	46.7	26.7	
- Represent good value for the product price	7	7	1	10	5	23.3	23.3	3.3	33.3	16.7	
- Satisfactory product review	6	3	4	10	7	20	10	13.3	33.3	23.3	
	10	5	0	5	10	33.3	16.7	0	16.7	33.3	
Buyer Motivation											
4. Motivation to buy second-hand products.											
- Environmental sustainability	12	8	2	8	10	40	26.7	6.7	26.7	33.3	
- Unique style and vintage appeal.	4	9	2	7	8	13.3	30	6.7	23.3	26.7	
- Supporting local charities or causes.	7	12	1	6	4	23.3	40	3.3	20	13.3	
- Cost effectiveness											
5. Recommend others to shop sustainably.	10	5	2	8	5	33.3	16.7	6.7	26.7	16.7	
	10	6	1	6	7	33.3	20	3.3	20	23.3	

Bold-font indicate high, and low inclinations towards factor agreeableness and disagreeableness

Table 3: Social, Mobile, Sustainability and Digital Apps (SMSDA) Factors and Themes

Themes	Description	Interview Excerpts
Social		
Decision making and collaboration.	Collaborative team decision-making in cohesion follows through with discussions, evaluation, and a feedback process.	<i>“It takes Hasna to discuss with the tailor, it takes Chad to look through the products and say wow, she's good, she's fast, she commits and then the whole team feeds back to me and Gunn, who is also our cofounder.”</i>
Community centric SE	People centric business model will improve community development when relevant work tools are used to improve customer-first interactions and deliver for the business repeatability expectation.	<i>“We are very people business, which means we deal with our customers. Personally, we speak to every one of them.”</i>
Social media for commerce convergence.	Refocusing SM support moving from dynamic content design to a platform that allows handling of orders, production, and delivery tailored according to the needs and demands of customers within resources conditions and constraints.	<i>“I would say our content on our SM like Instagram, FB and our website is very much random. We try our best to just squeeze in time to do content to be honest because we technically don't have the time to.”</i>

“Multi-Purpose Apps and the Social Media: What’s in it for the Sustainable Development Goals and Commerce to a Social Enterprise?”

Mobile		
Digital transformation	Using web application tools beyond the comfort zone would enhance tech-savviness and allow creative problem solving.	<i>“We all had to get creative. That was when we knew about LaLaMove; we engaged LalaMove. We knew about Easy Parcel; we engaged Easy Parcel. We knew about all these shortcuts of ways to reach out, to get things done using systems”.</i>
Adaptable learning culture	Adapting the business model with a pivot strategy that depends on the team dynamics, level of adaptability in the work task priorities and its approaches.	<i>“If one client A/B and C come at the same time, we have 3 different new products that have yet to be produced in our line. So, which means R&D, purchasing of new fabric, testing of the sewing are done. Then, once it's done by approval, then only we send to production. After production, QC is done. And then comes the packaging, the logo, the delivery, and every other bit of details from A to Z So, every new project comes a new challenge.”</i>
Sustainability		
Community empowerment	Acknowledging beneficiaries with multiple roles; potential trainers and self-employment for a career prospects.	<i>“They still run the show as part of as beneficiaries to receive job orders. However, we also empower them to be trainers themselves, which means that a tailor isn't just a tailor and when the pandemic hit, we easily did 30000 bucket face masks in a span of 11/2 years.”</i>
Training and skills building.	Teaching new skills free of charge to enhance capabilities and provide beneficiaries with job opportunities.	<i>“Then you can see them teaching the other akaks their skill sets of what they already learned and what they have already improved. And then they impart this knowledge to others. And then we also pay them a training fee as a trainer”.</i>

“Multi-Purpose Apps and the Social Media: What’s in it for the Sustainable Development Goals and Commerce to a Social Enterprise?”

Sustainable income generation	Product line that balances income strategy when business can be self-sustaining if focused on sustainable choices ie. upcycled or new materials strictly customizable in design, production and quality control, client centric.	<p>“If sustainable impact is what our clients are looking for, we can make it happen and our akak-akak gets the job at the end of the day, earning for themselves then that's where we are at.”</p> <p>“We are very strict, we are QC. Even though we are known as a social enterprise, we don't get our jobs out of pity.”</p>
Digital Apps		
SME Systems & Approach	Access to cost-effective web applications helps determine potential systems fit for a SME against the existing, available larger built, which are typically custom suited systems.	“We run on very free what's available and what's out there and easily available for smaller SME like us.”
Operations Efficiency	Managing operations using web tools to design, track orders and delivery for the organizational success.	“So, like Canva , it helps us design air table, it helps us track orders, Easy Parcel helps us do deliveries. So, all this was definitely picked up on during the pandemic and yeah, that's just how we work. ”
Resourceful Systems Use	Availability of free and easy to utilise systems improves managing production and deliveries given easy implementation in coherence with the work practice.	

Bold-font marked code words identified for themes derivation.

FINDINGS AND ARGUMENTS

General Survey Findings

Based on the anonymous survey data out of the 30 respondents in Table 2, 36.7% disagree to being familiar with the targets of the SDGs 17-goals, but 40% from the same group strongly agree in the influences of SDGs in their online buying decisions. A high 46.7% disagree that online items purchased are durable and long lasting, corresponding to a low total 30% of them agreeing in expectation of product quality and its’ price than anticipated. Additionally, based on online buying motives, 40% of the responses indicate commitment to support local charities and 33.3% believe in shopping responsibly and sourced cheaply (33.3%) online. It becomes easy to discuss their online purchases (33%) on SM sites as platforms to listen to every customer, understand their product experience and encourage feedback (Huang et al, 2023). A moderate difference of 6.7% from the group agreed to buying products online that have unique and vintage styles than others. Similarly, in the reflection of environmental sustainability considerations in buying behavior and influence, 40% of the respondents found to strongly agree to its importance.

Interview Findings

Based on the gathered survey responses in Table 2, online buying is perceived in a favorable light when observed in the context for a social cause, where in the aspects of SDGs and social consumerism these are recognized as important to the acceptance of conscious consumerism which betters with an influencer marketing strategy (Sheikh, 2023). Factors that relate to SDGs and commerce were categorized as themes; social, mobile, sustainability and digital apps and to each relevant themes as shown in Table 3 that derived from interview data with the founder of SE X, where firstly in (1) SM and web apps influence in ways of work associates with sub-themes of Digitals Apps where all three sub-themes derived ie. resourceful systems, SME systems approach and operations efficiency are found to associate with the SE’s choice in using free web apps to manage workflow and activities that associate favorably with the SME when having access to these tools. Additionally, the mobile factor in view of work flexibility at the SE find the digital web apps as a support to enhance creative means in problem solving as these apps are implemented as *shortcuts* to work execution from stages like *R&D, purchasing, testing, production, QC,*

“Multi-Purpose Apps and the Social Media: What’s in it for the Sustainable Development Goals and Commerce to a Social Enterprise?”

packaging to delivery influences decision for the right web technology adoption (Climent & Haftor, 2021). However being mobile transformative, digitally adaptive influences may appear to impair (3) sustaining business production effectively where in the implementation process of secure and suitable apps for multiple needs (Elsantil, 2020) challenges are significantly present on how to remain adaptable with its *people business* work culture and the right tools in a multi-tasking work environment as opposed to single-tasking work performance relating sub-theme adaptable learning culture when in consideration of time, cost while maintaining the expectation of quality standards (Adhiatma et al, 2022).

Next, when trying to adjust with relevant functions of multi-service-oriented apps used in the work routines, the social factor addresses sub-themes; collaborative decision making, and social media for commerce convergence that share common the traits of (2) SE staff readiness for technology use especially when *new projects and new challenges* presents the SE with client-focused project iterations irrespective of independent work involvement alike the silo workers to manage all handling orders, production and delivery when the *whole team feedbacks* brings to question to the coping mechanism on using a variety of these web apps to ensure input continuity flow for the outputs delivered especially when handling the process for larger projects and tracking purposes (Mink, 2023).

Further to this, with growing trends of SM as a commerce platform in view of the SE in expanding social network circles, the need to refocus its social selling formats is necessary not only for brand awareness, connecting communities and conversations (Friedrich et al., 2019) but as an approach for the business to drive-up average order value (Glaspie-Lundstrom, 2023) based on customer online buying preferences (Huang et al., 2022). Similarly, in (3) sustaining the business income sub-theme, producing sustainably made products provides the SE with an up-sell motive to diversify its product-line and assurance for business repeatability, here *strictly QC akak-akak gets the job, earning for themselves* however, such order requests cater a target segment from the

SE’s own client-base. On a positive note, skills building and training underlie as the sub-theme of sustainability where stakeholder relationships are developed here in the (2) readiness of the SE to provide job opportunities; to the beneficiaries and community with gains in economic values and work productivity when additional income is earned *teaching other akaks, paying them a training fee, producing 30000 face marks in 1½ years*, as ways used by the SE in their role to support B40 single mothers and homemakers and helping to the underserved community contributing to a circular economy following an adjustable business model in its value proposition to empower these woman through the digital means (Arshad et al., 2024) associating with the sub-theme community empowerment.

It is observed, in both (1) and (2) the SDG goals imply the working social mission that governs operations within SE, succinctly told in their sustainability actions. With growing public awareness and acceptance of ethical consumerism, more efforts need to be taken to tell the story right here through the SE and in their social impact measures (Dayangku, 2020).

PRESENTING THE SDGS THEMED WEB PORTAL

A web portal is proposed that would improve the approaches of sales and marketing for the SE where the system is expected to standardize how orders are processed from a system’s end point to avoid situations of staff working in silo and improving production capacity with large orders using a backend database system that will seamlessly pick up a sales order, added to cart, tracked until delivery using secure payment methods managed electronically. The system allows personalized orders integrating SDGs in the product designs and a feedback trail for quality improvement purposes. The portal is expected to reduce dependence over the use of multiple functional apps by the SE staff; improve communication with clients and visualize better of the current working ways in a proposed journey map shown in Figure 1 below.

Figure 1: Current vs. Proposed journey in an automate system flow from sales order to delivery.

CONCLUSION

The anticipation for the right or required web tools exemplifies the need to visualize the working process of an employee in consideration of factors like learning aptitude, flexibility, and timeliness. Having choices of web apps can be daunting to a new learner and detrimental when external factors such as competition and the disruptive nature of technologies alters the digitalization process and operational needs of a social enterprise in view of market demands. Here the paper limits for large data sampling than anonymous, while the survey observes anticipation and acceptability for the SDGs by consumers, the interview data represents management perception and expectation of business over social, mobile, sustainability and digital adaptable in a SME in their work practices by staff as values delivered. While important to ensuring the values of business is built for the causes in support of the underserved society, the role of a growing still SE steers in the direction and values of volunteerism while addressing a triple bottom line target. Business survivability improves with technology uses as demands becomes personalised, without compromising on quality, security where in the instance of a web system, authenticated access supplements with authorized end-users. Cost impact hinders most decisions for a full-fledged comprehensive system given the setting and scale of users where for the SE; smaller and for the limited users. Incorporating a web portal, would enhance opportunities with a new market, reach of customers and increasing demand however the limiting structure and production capacity does this away as with probability of enhancing order within the SE current market segment and significant client base. The other is ensuring that the values of SE can be transpired for greater acceptance and promotion of sustainable products and social consumerism positively.

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Appendix 1

Interview Protocol.

Role / Position of interviewee:

Location of the interview:

Date of the interview: Time of the interview :
.....

Thank you for participating in this study. The purpose of this research is to:

- Understand the current roles of a social enterprise in supporting the underprivileged communities.
 - Relate the influences of technologies, to transform and to scale in the business ways of working.
 - Refocus social impact through social consumerism and social media within the sustainability context.
1. What really got you started on this idea? (1) teaching a skill (2) building a skill (3) sustaining a skill (to transform)
 2. How did you identify your team and who they are? Are they also your beneficiaries? Could you share some of incidents that you could not forget, if not forgive when it comes to work and how they must be done?
 3. How much of social media is engaged by KTG and how has it changed since covid and the now the new internet normal (going all mobile the instant AI perhaps) today? How important is it for the current ways of working (ie. orders, production, delivery besides marketing)
 4. What are the challenges that you have faced in handling orders, production, and delivery? How have you and your team been coping, with more business clients, the supplies for materials and bringing a more visible end-to-end process from a business perspective and customer perspective?
 5. Do you feel the need to change the product line – from an exclusive edition to an affordable version for a wider customer base, hence changing the strategy for product pricing, managing cost and quality? How is business moving closer with technology in this aspect?
 6. Can you foresee production moving the entire supply chain itself changing towards upcycling and recycling alone as a long-term approach. How do you see the suppliers growing support if this shift happens.
 7. What are your hopes and future for your business?